

CORRELATION BETWEEN DIABETES AND PERIODONTAL HEALTH AFTER SCALING

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Abstract

Objective: To assess the impact of nonsurgical periodontal therapy on periodontal parameters in diabetic and non-diabetic individuals and to examine the association between HbA1c level changes and periodontal outcomes.

Study Design: Comparative observational study.

Place and Duration of the Study: Department of Periodontology, 21 Military Dental Center, Quetta, from December 2024-May, 2025.

Methodology: 220 patients were enrolled and divided into diabetic and non-diabetic groups. Clinical variables such as probing pocket depth (PPD), plaque index (PI), and gingival index (GI) were measured at baseline and three months following scaling and root planing. Glycemic control was determined by HbA1c levels at baseline and follow-up. The mean reductions in periodontal parameters were compared between the two groups, and correlation analyses were performed to assess the relationship between changes in HbA1c (Δ HbA1c) and improvements in periodontal indices (Δ PPD, Δ PI, Δ GI).

Results: Non-diabetic subjects showed much larger declines in PPD (Δ PPD = 1.13 mm versus 0.46 mm, $p < 0.001$) and GI (Δ GI = 0.38 versus 0.25, $p < 0.001$) than diabetic subjects, and the changes in PI were not significantly different ($p = 0.358$). Correlation analysis showed that Δ HbA1c was significantly correlated with Δ PPD ($r = 0.330$, $p < 0.001$) and Δ PI ($r = 0.251$, $p < 0.001$), but not significantly correlated with Δ GI ($r = -0.045$, $p > 0.05$).

Conclusion: Nonsurgical periodontal treatment enhances clinical periodontal parameters in diabetic as well as non-diabetic patients, with more improvement seen in non-diabetics. Improved glycemic control is linked with greater improvement in PPD and PI, emphasizing the need for coordinated periodontal and systemic diabetes management.

INTRODUCTION

Periodontal disease is a chronic inflammatory condition affecting the tooth supporting structures and it represents one of the most prevalent oral diseases throughout the world.¹ It is multifactorial and includes microbial biofilm, host immune response

and systemic factors. Of systemic diseases, diabetes mellitus is specifically associated with periodontal disease.² Diabetes, a metabolic disorder affecting immune response and wound healing allowing for periodontal tissue to be lost, is one such condition

associated with chronic hyperglycemia.³ The relationship is two-fold, since on the one hand diabetes increases the risk and severity of periodontitis and on the other hand periodontitis aggravates systemic inflammation and blood glucose control.⁴ This interplay prompts consideration of the evaluation of periodontal health in the context of metabolic disease.⁵

Strong epidemiological evidence has shown the two-way relationship between periodontitis and T2DM. Wu et al. (2020) showed that T2DM patients were 1.58 times more likely to have periodontitis (95% CI 1.38–1.81) compared with non-diabetic subjects. In addition, T2DM patients showed deeper PPW (0.61 mm), greater AL (0.89mm), and 2 less remaining teeth, on average.⁶ Furthermore, cohort studies confirmed the association of T2DM with 34% (RR = 1.34, 95% CI 1.11–1.61) increased risk for periodontitis, while severe periodontitis is associated with 53% (RR = 1.53, 95% CI 1.27–1.83) higher incidence of T2DM. The treatment of periodontitis has also been shown to improve glycaemia, with 0.27%–0.48% point decreases in HbA1c observed 3 months post-treatment.⁷ The frequency of periodontitis in T2DM individuals in the Ecuadorian cross-sectional study was 86.3%, and individuals with poor glycaemic control (HbA1c \geq 7%) were six times more likely to have periodontitis (OR = 6.67; 95% CI: 1.72–26.08).⁸

Although extensive literature has already demonstrated the bidirectional relationship between diabetes and periodontitis, there is currently an information gap in terms of the impact that periodontal treatment (scaling and root planing) exerts on the periodontal health status of diabetic subjects. Previous studies have focused primarily on the effect of therapy on glycemic control^{9,10} and have reported less often on the role of diabetes on periodontal healing, stability, and recurrence after regenerative therapy. An awareness of this is important for the development of holistic care plans for people with diabetes.

Therefore, the aim of the present study is to elucidate the correlation between periodontal health and diabetes after scaling and to investigate the manner by which the systemic metabolism state has influence on the results in periodontal therapy.

Methodology

This study was designed as a prospective observational study conducted at the 21 Military Dental Center (21 MDC), Quetta. The data collection period extended from December 2024 to May 2025. The sample size was calculated using WHO calculator for two independent means using a PPD reductions of 0.42–0.47 mm at 3 months following non-surgical periodontal therapy, a conservative between-group difference of 0.35 mm with a pooled standard deviation of 0.60 mm (Corbella et al.). Using a two-sample t-test with 80% power and 5% significance, the required sample was 93 participants per group (186 total). Allowing for 15% attrition, the final target sample size was set at 220 participants (110 per group). One of the convenience sampling methods was used to enlist eligible participants who attended the outpatient department for dental treatment during the study period.

Ethical clearance for this research was granted from the Armed Forces Postgraduate Medical Institute's Institutional Review Board. Before participation, all patients were given information on the aims and procedures of the study and were provided with written informed consent. Patient information was kept confidential during the study, and identifiers were de-identified for anonymity. Participants could withdraw from the study at any time without risking their routine care.

Inclusion criteria: age 30 years to 65 years; a clinical diagnosis of type 2 diabetes mellitus determined based on the value of HbA1c; a diagnosis of periodontitis, defined as having \geq 2 sites with probing pocket depth (PPD) of \geq 3 mm; and no history of periodontal therapy in the past 6 months.

Exclusion criteria: patients with any other systemic conditions that may have affected periodontal status (e.g., immunodeficient, cardiac diseases); pregnancy or lactation; history of smoking, any forms of drugs; no history of using tobacco in any form of long-term use of antibiotics or medicaments with inflammation in the past 3 months; receiving periodontal surgery in the previous year.

Baseline demographic information such as age and gender was documented, as well as the stage of diabetes for each participant. Glycated hemoglobin

(HbA1c) was assessed at baseline by a standard point-of-care finger-prick test analyzed with a portable HbA1c analyzer (clinical method). Based on the American Diabetes Association (ADA, 2024) and World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines, the participants were divided into normal (HbA1c < 5.7%), prediabetes (HbA1c 5.7% - 6.4%), or diabetes (HbA1c ≥ 6.5%). Periodontal parameters were measured at baseline and three months after scaling. Probing Pocket Depth (PPD) was assessed at six sites per tooth with a calibrated periodontal probe, and the mean values were calculated. Plaque Index (Silness and Løe, 1964)¹¹ and Gingival Index (Løe and Silness, 1963)¹² were assessed on four surfaces of all teeth. Scaling and root planing were performed using ultrasonic scalers by a single experienced periodontist to ensure uniform treatment. Patients were recalled after three months for follow-up measurement of PPD, Plaque Index, and Gingival Index. In each subject, the decrease in probing pocket depth (Δ PPD), plaque index (Δ PI), and gingival index (Δ GI) was determined by subtracting the 3-month post-scaling value from the baseline (Δ = baseline - 3-month).

To facilitate consistency, the examiner received calibration training before the study. Intra-examiner reliability was determined by the repetition of measurements in 10% of the sample one week later, and intra-class correlation coefficients (ICC) were computed to ensure reliability (>0.85 being acceptable). To reduce bias, the examiner making periodontal measurements did not know the patients' diabetic status and HbA1c value. Data were cross-checked by two separate investigators to minimize transcription errors. Measurement bias was minimized by examiner calibration and blinding. Information bias was minimized by employing

standardized indices of periodontal parameters and validated laboratory procedures for estimation of HbA1c. Attrition bias was minimized through reminders of follow-up by phone calls and rescheduling of missed appointments when possible.

Results

A total number of 220 patients included in the study had a mean age of 50.00 ± 10.15 years and 104 (47.27%) male and 116 (52.73%) female patients. Non-diabetic patients were younger, on average, than the diabetics (46.98 ± 9.45 years vs. 53.03 ± 9.97 years). HbA1c was lower in the non-diabetics (5.78 ± 0.33) than the diabetics (7.07 ± 0.27). Diabetic patients had higher baseline periodontal parameters (PPD, PI, GI) and at 3 months following scaling, non-diabetic patients showed larger decreases, mean PPD (2.09 ± 0.23 vs. 3.31 ± 0.13), PI (1.12 ± 0.14 vs. 1.51 ± 0.15), and GI (1.12 ± 0.09 vs. 1.45 ± 0.11) as indicated in **Table I**. Non-diabetic patients exhibited significantly larger decreases in probing pocket depth (Δ PPD: 3.22 ± 0.09 vs. 3.77 ± 0.26; $p < 0.001$) and gingival index (Δ GI: 1.37 ± 0.09 vs. 1.69 ± 0.12; $p < 0.001$). Decrease in plaque index (Δ PI) was higher in non-diabetics (1.61 ± 0.09 vs. 1.88 ± 0.13), but the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.358$) (**Table II**). Δ HbA1c was positively correlated with Δ PPD ($r = 0.330$, $p < 0.001$) and Δ PI ($r = 0.251$, $p < 0.001$), which means that higher decreases in HbA1c were related to larger improvements in probing depth and plaque index. There was no significant correlation between Δ HbA1c and Δ GI ($r = -0.045$, $p > 0.05$) as depicted in **Table III**.

Table I. Baseline and 3-month periodontal and glycemic parameters in non-diabetic and diabetic patients (Mean ± SD).

Variables	Diabetic Status	
	Non-diabetic Mean ± SD	Diabetic Mean ± SD
Age	46.98 ± 9.45	53.03 ± 9.97
HbA1c	5.78 ± 0.33	7.07 ± 0.27
PPD baseline	3.22 ± 0.09	3.77 ± 0.26
PI baseline	1.61 ± 0.09	1.88 ± 0.13
GI baseline	1.37 ± 0.09	1.69 ± 0.12
PPD 3 months	2.09 ± 0.23	3.31 ± 0.13

PI 3 months	1.12 ± 0.14	1.51 ± 0.15
GI 3 months	1.12 ± 0.09	1.45 ± 0.11

Table II. Comparison of mean changes (Δ) in periodontal parameters between non-diabetic and diabetic patients.

Variables	Diabetic Status		p - value
	Non-diabetic Mean ± SD	Diabetic Mean ± SD	
Δ PPD	3.22 ± 0.09	3.77 ± 0.26	<0.001
Δ PI	1.61 ± 0.09	1.88 ± 0.13	0.358
Δ GI	1.37 ± 0.09	1.69 ± 0.12	<0.001

Table III. Correlation matrix between changes in HbA1c (Δ HbA1c) and changes in periodontal parameters (Δ PPD, Δ PI, Δ GI).

Variables	Δ HbA1c	Δ PPD	Δ PI	Δ GI
Δ HbA1c	-	0.330*	0.251*	-0.045
Δ PPD	0.330*	-	-	-
Δ PI	0.251*	-	-	-
Δ GI	-0.045	-	-	-

Note: * represent significance difference ($p < 0.001$)

Discussion

This research found that nonsurgical periodontal treatment enhanced periodontal status in the two groups, with higher PPD reductions among non-diabetic patients (Δ PPD = 1.13 mm vs. 0.46 mm, $p < 0.001$). HbA1c decreases correlated positively with PPD ($r = 0.330$, $p < 0.001$) and plaque index ($r = 0.251$, $p < 0.001$) improvements. There was no significant correlation between HbA1c variation and gingival index ($r = -0.045$, $p > 0.05$).

A growing body of evidence positions our results within a homogeneous trend. Systematic reviews and meta-analyses indicate that non-surgical periodontal treatment achieves small but significant reductions in probing pocket depth (PPD) and decreases in inflammation, with pooled PPD reductions at ~ 0.3 – 0.6 mm at 3 months in mixed populations and consistent with the size of change noted in our cohort. For instance, pooled analysis demonstrated a mean reduction in PPD by around 0.31 mm at 3 months following scaling/root planning.¹³ Larger reviews of nonsurgical periodontal treatment also provide mean reductions in PPD in the order of ~ 0.47 mm at 3 months compared to no/little intervention.¹⁴ In terms of systemic glycemic impact, high-level syntheses document small but important reductions in HbA1c

following periodontal treatment in people with diabetes – a combined reduction of ~ 0.30 – 0.40% (by follow-up and included trials) was documented by Simpson et al.¹⁵ This is consistent with our finding that enhancement of glycemic control is more likely to follow enhanced healing of the periodontium.

Comparative investigations also uniformly reveal that diabetic individuals have poorer periodontal status at baseline (higher PPD, PI, GI and greater loss of attachment) and might get smaller absolute benefit from the same treatment when compared to non-diabetic individuals. Classical comparative research identified overwhelmingly larger periodontal severity among non-diabetics as compared to diabetics.¹⁶ Large population studies refer to increased chances of periodontal disease in individuals with diabetes (adjusted odds ~ 1.3 – 1.6), which means both increased burden and duration of disease in diabetic populations.¹⁷ These findings together can account for why our diabetic subgroup had lesser mean decreases in PPD and GI although they underwent the same SRP: the diabetic environment lowers the degree of clinical response.

Our finding that Δ HbA1c weakly correlated with Δ PPD ($r = 0.330$, $p < 0.001$) and even less with Δ PI (r

= 0.251, $p < 0.001$), with no significant correlation with ΔGI ($r = -0.045$, $p > 0.05$), agrees with current evidence of association between glycemic control and periodontal improvement but with variation in strength according to parameter and study design. Randomized trials and meta-analyses demonstrate that nonsurgical periodontal treatment generally results in modest decreases in HbA1c (~ 0.3 – 0.5% at 3 months) and associated clinical periodontal gains; these average effect sizes set the stage for anticipating moderate correlations instead of extremely large coefficients.¹⁸ For instance, Chen et al.'s meta-analysis indicated a weighted average HbA1c lowering of $\sim -0.51\%$ at 3 months post-periodontal treatment in diabetics, and previous pooled analyses have estimated reductions on the order of -0.36% ; such small systemic alterations typically yield correlation coefficients in the small-to-moderate range ($r \approx 0.2$ – 0.5).¹⁹

Clinical studies that have analyzed periodontal index-HbA1c relationships find similar patterns. Komatsu et al. reported robust baseline correlations between HbA1c and various periodontal measures (e.g., baseline PPD with HbA1c, $r = 0.563$, $p < 0.0001$) and also indicated that clinical indices of the inflamed surface area (PISA) correlated robustly with HbA1c and inflammatory biomarkers; when they analyzed changes subsequent to intensive therapy, reductions in inflammatory markers and PISA followed modest declines in HbA1c (~ 0.2 – 0.3%), and clinical-biochemical correlations were still statistically significant.²⁰ So, in that context, our ΔPPD $r = 0.330$ is smaller than the baseline PPD-HbA1c correlation reported by Komatsu (as would be expected, since cross-sectional correlations at baseline tend to be greater than correlations of change scores), yet within the range noted for change associations in interventional research where systemic reactions are modest.

Other observational evidence is also favorable to a positive association between pocket depth and glycemia. Tooi et al. found that average PPD was strongly related to HbA1c (regression $\beta \approx 0.38$, $p = 0.03$) in supportively treated patients, again suggesting a moderate association between periodontal severity and control of glycemia;²¹ this is consistent with our observation that changes in glycemia ($\Delta HbA1c$) follow changes in probing depth (ΔPPD). The lesser

correlation with plaque index (ΔPI $r = 0.251$) and lack of significant correlation with gingival index (ΔGI $r = -0.045$, ns) also align with earlier findings that report heterogeneous associations for surface-level inflammation/plaque indices. Plaque scores are also strongly dependent on short-term oral hygiene behavior and examiner differences, hence tend to be weaker and less reliable correlations with systemic glycemic indices than with pocket depth or PISA (which more immediately measure cumulative tissue destruction and inflamed periodontal surface). Cross-sectional and interventional research (and national surveys) most commonly report more robust, consistent associations for pocket depth/PISA and HbA1c compared with simple plaque or gingivitis redness indices.²²

Limitations

There were a number of limitations to this study. Firstly, the sample size was small and may therefore have reduced the statistical power to identify subtle associations, e.g., in cases like the gingival index (GI) where no correlation with HbA1c was found. Secondly, follow-up was for only three months; longer duration monitoring could have more clearly established stable change in HbA1c and periodontal outcomes. Thirdly, variables that might have confounded such as medication changes, changes in diet, and fluctuations in oral health habits between the study duration were not well controlled and may have affected both the glycemic as well as the periodontal parameters. Finally, since this study was performed at a single center, the results' generalizability to other larger populations is still limited.

Conclusion

Within the confines of this study, it may be concluded that nonsurgical periodontal treatment causes important gains in probing pocket depth (PPD), plaque index (PI), and gingival index (GI) in diabetic and non-diabetic patients with greater gains in non-diabetics. Additionally, decreases in HbA1c values were significantly correlated with gains in PPD and PI, implying that enhanced control of glycaemia is linked with more positive periodontal outcomes.

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21 Military Dental Center, Quetta

Conflict of Interest

None

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